

Zero Sequence Line Parameter Estimation Using PMU Data Considering Uncertainty Factors

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Abstract—Synchronized Measurement Technology has significantly advanced real-time monitoring and control applications for power system control centers. A key component, the Phasor Measurement Unit (PMU), is now widely deployed in transmission systems, enhancing system monitoring and control. PMU-rich systems also enable the refinement of critical modeling parameters, such as transmission line sequence parameters, used in control center applications and substation protection relays. This paper discusses the estimation of zero-sequence parameters of transmission lines, essential for fault analysis in control centers and distance protection relays. Two key factors impacting estimation accuracy are examined, namely the PMU measurement and fault location uncertainties. Their effects on zero sequence line parameter estimation accuracy and consequently on the performance of distance relays are analyzed in the IEEE 9-bus system.

Keywords—Distance relay, faults, PMU measurements, transmission lines, zero sequence impedance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern power systems face increasing challenges due to the high penetration of renewable energy sources and the increasing electricity demand driven by the electrification of transportation and heating/cooling sectors. This evolving landscape necessitates robust and reliable methodologies for monitoring, securing, and controlling the modern power systems.

Synchronized Measurement Technology (SMT), having as a key element the Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs), has revolutionized grid operations. PMUs provide high-fidelity, synchronized measurements of voltage and current phasors, enabling critical applications such as linear state estimation [1], wide-area control [2], and inertia estimation [3]. This enhanced situational awareness empowers grid operators to navigate the complexities of modern, low-inertia power systems. PMU deployment is steadily increasing across transmission systems, with some grids achieving full observability. This expansion aligns with the long-term plans of electric utilities to enhance their measurement infrastructure performance [4].

Beyond real-time monitoring and control, PMU measurements can be used for refining power system models. Specifically, synchronized measurements facilitate accurate estimation of line parameters when PMUs are installed at both ends of a transmission line [5]. Typically, transmission lines are modelled as pi-equivalent circuit with series and shunt lumped parameters. These parameters are initially calculated

based on factors such as line structure, conductor material, phase configuration, and manufacturer data [6]. However, these calculated values may not accurately reflect the actual line parameters due to various factors.

In reality, transmission line parameters are influenced by environmental factors (e.g., temperature, soil resistivity) [7], modelling inaccuracies (e.g., parallel line coupling), and construction variations. Furthermore, human factors can contribute to inaccuracies in parameter databases, such as unreported network configuration changes or errors in line length calculations. Some studies have reported significant discrepancies between actual and stored line parameter values, with errors reaching up to 30% [8]. Such inaccuracies can degrade the accuracy of monitoring applications and limit the situational awareness of power system operators. Moreover, erroneous line parameters can compromise the reliability of distance protection schemes, as these parameters are crucial inputs for relay settings.

Several methods have been proposed to address the issue of erroneous line parameters. These methods typically involve identifying lines with inaccurate parameters, often based on techniques like the "Largest Normalized Residuals" test derived from Weighted Least Squares (WLS) state estimator results [9]. Other approaches utilize Lagrangian multipliers [10] or strategic PMU placement [11] to pinpoint erroneous parameters in critical network configurations.

Various methods have also been developed to correct identified erroneous line parameters using SCADA or PMU measurements. While SCADA-based methods provide valuable insights [12], more precise parameter estimation can be achieved using synchronized PMU measurements. Some approaches require PMU installations at both ends of a transmission line [5] while others explore parameter estimation with PMU measurements at a single line end, considering scenarios where not all lines have PMUs at both ends [13].

It's important to note that these methods primarily focus on positive sequence parameters, as measurements are typically collected under normal operating conditions. However, accurate estimation of zero sequence line parameters is crucial for reliable ground fault protection. This necessitates utilizing measurements during fault conditions, specifically when unbalanced ground faults (single-line or double-line to ground) occur, resulting in zero sequence currents within the system.

Existing methods for zero sequence parameter estimation include approaches using data from protection relays [14] and methods utilizing PMU measurements for mutually coupled lines [15]. However, these methods may face limitations, such as the use of unsynchronized relay data, requiring subsequent synchronization techniques, or they neglect the relatively high PMU measurement errors during transient events [16].

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This paper considers two key uncertainty factors that can significantly impact the accuracy of zero sequence parameter estimation, namely the measurement uncertainty, associated with PMU data during transient events (e.g., ground faults), and the fault location uncertainty associated with the inaccuracies in determining the precise fault location along the faulty line. A sensitivity analysis is conducted to quantify the impact of these uncertainty factors on the estimated zero sequence impedance. Furthermore, the study investigates the implications of these uncertainties on the performance of distance protection relays through a case study in the IEEE 9-bus system.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II provides background information on zero sequence line parameter estimation during single-line-to-ground faults. Section III discusses the two uncertainty factors considered in the sensitivity analysis. Section IV presents the results of the sensitivity analysis and evaluates the impact on distance protection. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. ZERO SEQUENCE PARAMETER ESTIMATION THROUGH PMU MEASUREMENTS

Three-phase transmission lines are commonly represented using self and mutual impedance values, as depicted in Fig. 1. For a fully transposed transmission line, it is assumed that the self-impedances of all three phases are equal, and the mutual impedances between the phases are also identical. Under this assumption, a fully transposed three-phase transmission line can be modelled using a series phase impedance matrix, expressed as [6],

$$\mathbf{Z}_P = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{aa} & Z_{ab} & Z_{ab} \\ Z_{ab} & Z_{aa} & Z_{ab} \\ Z_{ab} & Z_{ab} & Z_{aa} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where, with reference to Fig. 1,

$$Z_{aa} = R_a + jX_a \quad (2)$$

$$Z_{ab} = R_{ab} + jX_{ab} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1: Three phase transmission line pi-model

To perform unbalanced three-phase analysis, particularly for scenarios involving unbalanced faults, a linear transformation from the phase components to symmetrical components is required. This transformation enables decoupled analysis of positive, negative, and zero-sequence components. The series phase impedance matrix (\mathbf{Z}_P) is transformed into the sequence impedance matrix (\mathbf{Z}_S) as,

$$\mathbf{Z}_S = \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & a & a^2 \\ 1 & a^2 & a \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} Z_{aa} & Z_{ab} & Z_{ab} \\ Z_{ab} & Z_{aa} & Z_{ab} \\ Z_{ab} & Z_{ab} & Z_{aa} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & a^2 & a \\ 1 & a & a^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where $a = 1 \angle 120^\circ$.

For a fully transposed transmission line, the resulting sequence impedance matrix \mathbf{Z}_S is diagonal, as shown below,

$$\mathbf{Z}_S = \begin{bmatrix} Z_0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & Z_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Z_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where, Z_0, Z_1, Z_2 is the zero, positive and negative sequence series impedance, respectively.

Positive-sequence impedance Z_1 can be calculated using PMU data obtained during the steady-state operation of the power system. Additionally, the negative-sequence impedance Z_2 is generally assumed to be equal to the positive-sequence impedance. However, estimating the zero-sequence impedance, Z_0 , presents unique challenges, as it cannot be determined under normal, balanced operating conditions. This is because zero-sequence currents require a return path, which typically occurs during unbalanced ground faults.

To estimate the zero-sequence impedance, it is necessary to analyze the system conditions during unbalanced ground faults, such as single or double line-to-ground faults. In this work, the focus is placed on single line to ground faults, specifically considering a fault in phase A, without loss of generality. The analysis, however, can be inclusive and the same results are expected for double line-to-ground faults or single line to ground faults in other phases.

In the case of the zero-sequence impedance estimation, two distinct cases are explored:

1. **Fault on the line of interest:** In this case, a single line-to-ground fault occurs directly on the transmission line where the zero-sequence parameters are to be estimated.
2. **Fault elsewhere in the system:** In this case, the fault occurs elsewhere in the power system, rather than on the line of interest. Such case requires a different approach to infer the zero-sequence line parameters.

The following sections detail the methodologies and mathematical formulations for zero-sequence impedance estimation under these two cases.

A. Fault on the line of interest

When a single line-to-ground fault occurs on the transmission line of interest, the zero-sequence line behavior can be analyzed using the zero-sequence equivalent circuit shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Zero-sequence transmission line diagram with a fault at distance x from bus

Assuming the fault occurs at a distance x (expressed as a fraction of the total line length) from the sending bus s , the voltage phasor at the fault location can be determined using synchronized PMU measurements (voltage and current phasors) taken at both ends of the line as,

$$V_0^F = V_0^s - I_0^s x Z_0 \quad (6)$$

$$V_0^F = V_0^r - I_0^r (1-x) Z_0 \quad (7)$$

where, V_0^F, V_0^r, V_0^s is the zero sequence voltage phasor at the line fault point, receiving and sending line end respectively; while I_0^s and I_0^r is sending and receiving zero sequence current phasor. It should be noted that the zero sequence

measurements can be calculated through the phase quantities provided by the PMUs.

Since the voltage phasor at the fault point (V_0^F), must be the same from both perspectives, (6) and (7) can be equated. By doing so, the unknown voltage at the fault point, which is often difficult to measure due to the presence of an unknown fault resistance, is eliminated. This yields the line zero-sequence impedance that can be calculated as [14],

$$Z_0 = \frac{V_0^s - V_0^r}{I_0^s x - (1-x)I_0^r} \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) shows that the zero-sequence impedance estimation relies on PMU-measured current and voltage phasors at both ends of the line and the fault location parameter x , which represents the relative distance of the fault from the sending bus. Both factors are critical for precise zero-sequence impedance estimation in this case.

B. Fault elsewhere in the system

If the single line-to-ground fault occurs elsewhere in the power system, rather than on the transmission line of interest, zero-sequence currents will still flow through the line toward the fault location. In such cases, the zero-sequence equivalent circuit of the line can be simplified, as shown in Fig. 3. The zero-sequence impedance can then be estimated as,

$$Z_0 = \frac{V_0^s - V_0^r}{I_0^s} \quad (9)$$

This method does not rely on the fault location x , as the zero-sequence current flows through the entire line uniformly toward the fault. Here, the PMU measurements at the sending and receiving ends of the line are sufficient to estimate the zero-sequence impedance.

Fig. 3: Single line zero-sequence transmission line diagram without a fault

In both fault scenarios, the zero-sequence shunt admittance is neglected. This simplification is valid because the zero-sequence shunt admittance is typically much smaller compared to the series zero-sequence impedance parameters. As a result, its impact on the estimation process is negligible and does not compromise accuracy [6].

III. FACTORS THAT AFFECT THE ZERO-SEQUENCE LINE PARAMETER ESTIMATION

The accurate estimation of zero-sequence parameters in transmission lines is influenced by two primary factors: the uncertainty associated with PMU measurements and the uncertainty in fault location. Both factors can significantly affect the precision of the calculated zero-sequence line parameters under different operating scenarios. The first factor, PMU measurement uncertainty, is relevant to both cases discussed in the previous sections since PMU data is used in the formulation of equations (8) and (9). The second factor, fault location uncertainty, pertains specifically to cases where the fault occurs within the transmission line of interest. Based on (8), inaccuracies in determining the fault location introduce an additional layer of error in the estimation of the zero-sequence parameters. This section discusses the two

critical uncertainty factors, highlighting their sources and implications for zero-sequence parameter estimation.

A. PMU measurement uncertainties

The uncertainties associated with measurements arise from the equipment used to obtain them, particularly when real-world phenomena deviate from the abstract model employed by the measurement system. For PMU measurements, the measurement chain consists of two key components: the instrument transformers and the PMU itself. Instrument transformers step down the grid voltage and current to levels acceptable for the PMU, while the PMU processes these inputs to derive synchronized phasor measurements. Both components introduce uncertainties that can be quantified using two standard methods: the Type A and Type B evaluation methods [17].

The Type A evaluation method estimates uncertainty by analyzing repeated observations of the measurement process under identical operational and environmental conditions. However, this approach is impractical for power systems due to constantly changing conditions. The Type B evaluation method, on the other hand, assesses uncertainty based on manufacturers' data about the measurement chain components. In this approach, errors are treated as random variables, but their distributions must be known. Manufacturers typically provide error bounds for both the instrument transformers and PMUs, without information about error distributions. In such cases, the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurements (GUM) [18] recommends assuming a uniform error distribution. It should be noted that uniform error distribution is more appropriate for random fluctuations within an uncertainty range, while for GPS time synchronization issues or instrument transformer dynamic errors a more advanced modelling is needed.

For estimating zero-sequence line parameters, PMU measurements must accurately capture the transient behavior of voltage and current at both ends of the transmission line. According to the IEEE standard for synchrophasors [16], PMUs must achieve a Total Vector Error (TVE) of less than 1% during steady-state conditions, which is comparable to the maximum errors introduced by instrument transformers. However, during dynamic conditions, PMU errors are significantly larger. Table 1 summarizes the maximum allowable TVE and its decomposition into magnitude and phase angle errors under dynamic conditions [16].

Table 1. PMU Maximum Errors under Dynamic Conditions

Measurement Type	Max TVE (%)	Magnitude (%)	Phase Angle (degrees)
Voltage	8	± 5.4	± 3.3
Current	3	± 1.6	± 1.44255

During transient conditions, the magnitude and angle errors associated with PMU measurements dominate over the uncertainties introduced by instrument transformers. Therefore, the uncertainty model for PMU measurements during dynamic conditions neglects instrument transformer uncertainties. The PMU quantities can be expressed as [17],

$$V_{meas} = V_{act}(1 + unif(\bar{e}_{PMU}^V)) \quad (10)$$

$$I_{meas} = I_{act}(1 + unif(\bar{e}_{PMU}^I)) \quad (11)$$

$$\varphi_{meas} = \varphi_{act} + unif(\bar{e}_{PMU}^\varphi) \quad (12)$$

$$\theta_{meas} = \theta_{act} + unif(\bar{e}_{PMU}^\theta), \quad (13)$$

where, $unif(\cdot)$ denotes a symmetric uniform distribution with zero mean, whose limits are defined by the values in

parentheses. In (10)-(13), random samples from the uniform distribution introduce random errors into the PMU measurements. The parameters \bar{e}_{PMU}^V , and \bar{e}_{PMU}^I represent the maximum errors in voltage and current magnitudes, while \bar{e}_{PMU}^ϕ , \bar{e}_{PMU}^θ represent the maximum errors in voltage and current phase angles. These errors, expressed as percentages, are derived from Table 1. Consequently, the actual voltage and current magnitudes (V/I_{act}) are treated as error-free quantities entering the PMU and are multiplied by a random sample from the uniform distribution to simulate measurement errors.

B. Fault location uncertainty

The second major factor affecting the estimation of zero-sequence parameters is the uncertainty in fault location, particularly when the fault occurs within the line of interest. For a single-line-to-ground fault, the fault location is usually expressed as a distance ratio, x from one of the line's terminals (e.g., bus s). Accurate determination of this fault location is crucial for applying (8) to calculate the zero-sequence parameters. However, pinpointing the exact fault location is challenging due to several influencing factors.

Firstly, the presence of fault resistance alters the fault current and voltage profiles, making it difficult to accurately determine the fault location from simple measurements, as discussed in [19]. Additionally, the assumptions embedded within the fault location algorithms, especially those related to fault resistance, contribute to the uncertainty. Furthermore, measurement noise, which is inherent in the data used for fault location calculations, enlarge this uncertainty, making precise fault location determination even more difficult [20].

To account for these uncertainties, the fault location x is often treated as a random variable within a bounded range. Similar to PMU measurement uncertainties, fault location uncertainty can be modelled using a uniform distribution, depending on the available data and assumed error bounds. To model the fault location uncertainty in sensitivity analyses, the following expression can be considered,

$$x = x_{act}(1 + unif(\Delta x)) \quad (14)$$

where, x_{act} is the true fault location, $unif(\Delta x)$ represents the symmetric uniform distribution with a zero mean, and Δx denotes the error bounds for the fault location.

It should be noted that typical protection relays use impedance based methods for calculating the fault location. They actually measure the voltage and current seen by the one end of the line for calculating the apparent impedance and then they compare it with the known line apparent impedance.

IV. CASE STUDIES AND DISCUSSION

The sensitivity analysis for the estimation of zero-sequence line parameters, considering the two uncertainty factors outlined in the previous section, was conducted on the IEEE 9-bus system [21]. The system was implemented in DiGSILENT PowerFactory, including dynamic generator models. All the details regarding the positive and zero sequence parameters for the system can be found in [21]. As illustrated in Fig. 4, two single-line-to-ground faults were analyzed (one at a time) on different lines. The first fault (Fault 1) occurs on the line connecting bus 8 to bus 9 at 84% of the line length from bus 8, while the second fault (Fault 2) occurs on the line connecting bus 5 to bus 4 at 37% of the line length from bus 5. Each fault lasts 0.2 seconds. This section analyzes the impact of PMU measurement uncertainty and fault

location uncertainty on the estimation of zero-sequence parameters and examines how they affect the operation of a distance protection relay. It is assumed that PMU measurements are available at both ends of the transmission lines, with a reporting rate of 50 phasors per second.

Fig. 4. IEEE 9-bus system

A. Case study 1-PMU measurement uncertainty

In this case study, various maximum PMU errors, ranging from 0% to the maximum dynamic error specified in Table 1 are considered. PMU measurements were generated using equations (10)-(13), while the fault location was assumed known. To eliminate biases introduced by measurement uncertainty, 500 Monte Carlo simulations were performed for each maximum error scenario. The accuracy of zero-sequence parameter estimation was quantified using the mean absolute error (MAE) of the impedance magnitude, defined as:

$$MAE_{|Z_0|} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \left| \frac{|Z_{0,act}| - |Z_{0,est}^{t,m}|}{|Z_{0,act}|} \right| \right) \quad (15)$$

where M is the number of Monte Carlo simulations, N is the number of PMU measurements during the fault, $|Z_{0,act}|$ is the actual zero-sequence impedance magnitude, and $|Z_{0,est}^{t,m}|$ is the estimated value at time step t during the fault in the m -th simulation. In the following case studies it was implicitly assumed that the zero sequence impedance does not vary during faults. Thus, the estimated impedance in each time step during fault is used for calculating a mean value for the zero sequence impedance for the whole fault duration.

For Fault 1, the zero-sequence impedance of the line 8-9 was calculated using (8), while for the remaining lines, (9) was applied. Fig. 5 shows the MAE of the zero-sequence impedance magnitude for all lines in the system under four different maximum error scenarios (fractions of the maximum error specified in Table 1).

As it shown in Fig. 5, when PMU measurements are error-free, the MAE for all lines is relatively small, indicating that the zero-sequence impedance can be accurately estimated during a single-line-to-ground fault. However, as the PMU measurement error increases, the estimation accuracy decreases significantly, particularly for the lines connecting buses 4-5 and 5-7. This result highlights that even a fraction of the maximum PMU error specified in [16] can negatively impact the estimation accuracy for certain lines.

Further analysis reveals that the zero-sequence impedance is more sensitive to PMU errors for lines carrying smaller zero-sequence current contributions to the fault. For example, in Fault 1, the zero-sequence current contribution from generator G1 flows predominantly through lines 4-6 and 6-9, while relatively less current flows through lines 4-5 and 5-7.

As a result, PMU measurement errors have a more pronounced effect on the impedance estimation of lines with smaller zero-sequence currents.

Fig. 5. MAE of the zero sequence impedances magnitude-Fault 1

This trend is also evident in the Fault 2 case. As shown in Fig. 6, the estimation of zero-sequence impedance is significantly compromised by PMU measurement errors in lines 7-8 and 8-9. In this scenario, the zero-sequence current contributions from generators G2 and G3 primarily flow through lines 5-7 and 6-9, respectively. Consequently, the smaller zero-sequence currents in lines 7-8 and 8-9 are more heavily impacted by PMU errors, leading to greater inaccuracies in the estimated impedance.

Fig. 6. MAE of the zero sequence impedances magnitude-Fault 2

In general, the results of this sensitivity analysis highlight that PMU measurement uncertainties should be taken into consideration particularly for lines with low zero-sequence current contributions during phase to ground faults. Further, there are some lines that exhibit estimation error in the case where no PMU error is assumed. This estimation error can be attributed to the modelling uncertainties of the line during fault conditions, but this is out of the scope of this work.

B. Case study 2-Fault location uncertainty

This case study focuses on lines where a fault occurs within their range, aiming to analyze the impact of fault location uncertainty on the accurate calculation of zero-sequence impedance using (8). For this analysis, it was assumed that PMU measurements are error-free. Fault locations were generated using (14), with fault location deviations (Δx) of 2%, 5%, 10%, and 20%.

For Fault 1, the MAE of the zero-sequence impedance estimation for the line connecting buses 8 and 9 is shown in Fig. 7a. The results indicate that for fault deviations up to 5%, the MAE remains within acceptable limits. However, when the fault location deviation exceeds 10%, the MAE increases significantly, leading to substantial errors in the zero-sequence impedance estimation. Similarly, in the case of Fault 2, the accuracy of the zero-sequence impedance estimation deteriorates notably for fault location deviations beyond 5%, as depicted in Fig. 7b.

Fig. 7: MAE of zero-sequence impedance magnitude for lines 8-9 and 4-5 when Fault 1 and Fault 2 occurs respectively

C. Impact of zero sequence estimation error on distance relay operation

The zero-sequence impedance plays a crucial role in the operation of distance protection relays during unbalanced ground faults. One key setting in these relays is the zero-sequence compensation factor (K_0) [15], calculated as,

$$K_0 = \frac{Z_0 - Z_1}{KZ_1} \quad (16)$$

where K takes values between 1 and 3, depending on the relay design. This factor compensates for the zero-sequence current measured by the relay, enabling it to correctly calculate the apparent impedance seen at the sending end of the line. The relay measures the impedance as the ratio of the sending-end phase voltage to the sending-end phase current (i.e., $\frac{V_A}{I_A}$). During fault conditions, when the current contains a zero-sequence component, K_0 ensures that the apparent impedance matches the actual positive-sequence impedance.

If the compensated impedance seen by the relay is smaller than its “reach” (typically 80–90% of the positive-sequence impedance for the primary protection zone), the relay detects the fault and trips. For a single line-to-ground fault, the compensated apparent impedance is calculated as,

$$Z_{comp} = \frac{V_A}{I_A + K_0 I_0} \quad (17)$$

It is apparent that in case Z_0 is miscalculated it will compromise the reliability of the relay operation. In this case two different scenarios were analyzed for line 8-9, to evaluate the impact of zero sequence impedance estimation errors on the distance relay operation.

Scenario 1: Zero-sequence impedances were calculated considering the PMU measurement uncertainties, as shown in Fig. 6. Four cases were considered, corresponding to the different MAEs for line 8-9, indicated in Fig. 6.

Scenario 2: Zero sequence impedances were derived based on fault location uncertainties for line 8-9 as illustrated in Fig. 7a. Four cases were considered, corresponding to fault location deviations of 2%, 5%, 10% and 20%.

For both scenarios, the estimated zero-sequence impedances were used as inputs to the relay installed at bus 8, with a reach of 90% of the positive-sequence impedance of line 8-9. Fault 1 was applied, and the relay operation was evaluated, as shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2: Distance relay operation for Scenario 1

Estimated Z_0 PMU measurement uncertainty	Relay operation
No error	Trip
Max error/4	Trip
Max error/2	No trip
Max error	No trip

Table 3: Distance relay operation for Scenario 2

Estimated Z_0 Fault location uncertainty	Relay operation
2%	Trip
5%	Trip
10%	No trip
20%	No trip

The results from both tables highlight the critical importance of accurately estimating the zero-sequence impedance for reliable relay operation. In Scenario 1, relay operation was unaffected for PMU measurement errors up to a quarter of the maximum specified value in Table 1. However, larger errors caused the zero-sequence impedance estimation to deviate significantly, leading to relay maloperation. Similarly, in Scenario 2, fault location accuracy played a significant role. Fault location deviations exceeding 10% compromised the zero-sequence impedance estimation, resulting in relay maloperation during faults. These findings show the imperative need for precise PMU measurements and fault location accuracy to ensure the reliable performance of distance protection relay. In this direction, an adaptive approach for updating Z_0 and Z_1 in the relay based on real time information received by the PMUs could mitigate these issues.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigates the estimation of zero-sequence impedance parameters of transmission lines using PMU measurements. In particular, the paper focuses on the impact of PMU measurement uncertainties and fault location errors to the estimation accuracy of the zero-sequence impedance. The sensitivity analysis related to the PMU measurement uncertainties (transient conditions) revealed that the accuracy of zero-sequence impedance estimation is significantly influenced for larger PMU measurement uncertainties, especially in lines with lower contributions to the fault current. Further, the sensitivity analysis regarding the fault location uncertainty showed that deviations in fault location beyond 5% introduce errors in zero-sequence impedance estimation.

It is also demonstrated that both PMU measurement and fault location uncertainties have an indirect impact on the reliable operation of distance protection relays, since accurate estimation of zero-sequence impedance is essential. Errors in parameter estimation, whether from measurement uncertainties or fault location deviations exceeding 10%, resulted in relay maloperation. Future work will concentrate on developing adaptive estimation techniques and advanced protection schemes that account for these uncertainty factors, considering more complex structure with parallel lines.

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